

Appendix 3

Count of publisher

22

Year	Published	%
Year-2016	1	5%
Year-2017	1	5%
Year-2018	1	5%
Year-2019	3	14%
Year-2020	2	9%
Year-2021	6	27%
Year-2022	5	23%
Year-2023	3	14%
Grand Total	22	

Row Labels	Count of publisher	%
Brazil	1	5%
Canada	4	18%
China	3	14%
Germany	3	14%
Hong Kong	1	5%
Ireland	1	5%
Japan	1	5%
Russia	1	5%
Saudi Arabia	1	5%
Taiwan	1	5%
United States	5	23%
Grand Total	22	

Row Labels	Count of publisher	%
PubMed	8	36%
Scopus	14	64%
Grand Total	22	

Type of Study	No. of study
Randomized controlled trial	8
Evaluation study	5
Development and evaluation study	4
prospective comparative study	1
RCT Quasi-experimental study	1
Usability Testing	1
validation study	1
(blank)	1
Grand Total	22

Row Labels	Machine Learning/Deep Learning	Machine Learning	Robotic Skills Training	virtual Reality	Grand Total
Behavioural Health				1	1
Ophthalmology		1			1
Orthopaedics		1		1	2
Surgery	1	2	2	2	7
Surgery/Medicine				1	1
Training Lab	1	5		4	10
Grand Total	2	9	2	9	22

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